

Interfacial Tension of Binary H-Bonded Liquids and Autocomplexing in an Aqueous CdI_2

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The interesting anomalous behaviour of alcohols and esters having four or more carbon atoms was explained on the basis of the reversal of the electrical double layer at the oil-water interface and further that these liquids have a ring structure through H-bond¹. At the interface of such a liquid and a salt solution, there is a preferential adsorption of one or the other ion creating double layer potential difference. The H-bond ring structure of liquids such as amyl or butyl acetate is sensitive to the changes in ionic character of the salt solution². When interfacial tension (I.T.) of increasing concentration of aqueous cupric chloride is measured against isoamyl acetate, the curves show peaks corresponding to autocomplexing³. Such I.T. measurements of aqueous cadmium iodide against esters indicated peaks corresponding to CdI_3 and CdI_4^- ions⁴. The existence of these complex ions of copper and cadmium have been also shown by monovariation method using mixed solutions of cupric chloride or cadmium iodide with respective alkali halides⁵.

The object of the present work is to show that the H-bond structure of binary mixture of butyl alcohol or isoamyl alcohol with chloroform or methylaniline or aniline or citronenol or any such binary, combination is susceptible to ionic changes besides the esters mentioned having H-bond ring structure and so the interfacial tension of increasing cadmium iodide concentration when measured shows two maxima for a H-bonded pair of liquids, because variation in interfacial tension is effected by ionic changes due to autocomplexing.

Isoamyl alcohol or chloroform or any such H-bond forming liquid does not individually show such peaks. Amyl acetate with carbon tetrachloride or benzene each 50% and not forming H-bond when mixed with each other also do not show such peaks. However, any two liquids forming H-bond between H-atom of one liquid molecule and donor atom with lone-pair of electrons of the other liquid molecule when mixed, the mixture shows two peaks, when the interfacial tension of such a mixture is measured against increasing concentration of cadmium iodide (Fig. 1).

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The liquids

were freshly distilled and the salt solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

Fig. 1. Plots of vol. of one drop vs concn. of CdI_2 : (e) butyl alcohol + chloroform (1:1), (f) isoamyl alcohol + citronenol (1:1), (g) isoamyl alcohol + methylaniline (1:1) and (h) isoamyl alcohol + aniline.

The drop volume method was used to determine interfacial tension of pure liquids or mixtures at room temperature (30°) using an Agla micrometer syringe (Burrrows Welcome, London).

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